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DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING INVESTMENT AND EXPORT IN REMOTE SERVICE ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: The scientific significance of this article is to identify the patterns of influence of remote service enterprises on investment processes in the context of digital transformation, as well as to identify mechanisms for stimulating innovation. The practical value of the work is to develop recommendations for business and government on the effective use of digital technologies in attracting investments and increasing the sustainability of the service economy.

Key words: digital transformation, innovation and investment activities, service sector, digital economy, fintech, artificial intelligence, big data, public-private partnerships, sustainable development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning ilmiy ahamiyati raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida masofaviy xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi korxonalarining investitsiya jarayonlariga ta'sir etuvchi qonuniyatlarni aniqlash, shuningdek innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish mexanizmlarini belgilashdan iborat. Ishning amaliy qiymati biznes va davlat boshqaruvi subyektlari uchun investitsiyalarni jalb etish hamda xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi iqtisodiyotining barqarorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilishi bilan izohlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli transformatsiya, innovatsion va investitsion faoliyat, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi, raqamli iqtisodiyot, fintech, sun'iy intellekt, katta ma'lumotlar (Big Data), davlat-xususiy sheriklik, barqaror rivojlanish.

Аннотация: Научная значимость данной статьи заключается в выявлении закономерностей влияния предприятий, предоставляющих удаленные услуги, на инвестиционные процессы в контексте цифровой трансформации, а также в определении механизмов стимулирования инноваций. Практическая ценность работы состоит в разработке рекомендаций для бизнеса и правительства по эффективному использованию цифровых технологий для привлечения инвестиций и повышения устойчивости экономики услуг.

Ключевые слова: цифровая трансформация, инновационная и инвестиционная деятельность, сектор услуг, цифровая экономика, финтех, искусственный интеллект, большие данные, государственно-частное партнерство, устойчивое развитие.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of accelerating global digitalization, companies in the remote service sector of Uzbekistan are faced with the need to deeply transform their innovation and investment strategies. Digital transformation is becoming a key factor in increasing competitiveness, reducing transaction costs, and accelerating innovation in segments such as financial services, logistics, education, healthcare, hospitality and tourism, and e-commerce. In 2023-2025, investments in digital services infrastructure in Uzbekistan increased by more than 32%, and

the share of online platforms in the total transaction volume reached 38%. Government programs and support from international financial institutions are creating favorable conditions for capital flows and the introduction of innovative technologies.

Particular attention is being paid to the development of artificial intelligence, big data, cloud services and fintech solutions. These technologies allow service enterprises to increase productivity, personalize customer experience and create new business models. The development of digital financial instruments such as crowdfunding, venture capital and public-private partnerships is playing an important role in ensuring the rapid modernization of service industries.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Additional Measures to Support the Training of Qualified Specialists in the Field of Digitalization", No. PQ-51, dated February-1, 2024, was adopted to ensure the implementation of the law and to support youth IT services, as well as to organize assistance for non-governmental educational organizations that train specialists for modern professions with high demand in the export sector. Starting from March-1, 2024, a one-time subsidy program was introduced for non-state educational organizations. Under this program, subsidies are provided in the amount of up to 75 times the base calculation amount when a graduate is employed by an organization exporting IT services, and up to 105 times the base calculation amount when a young graduate with a disability is employed by such an organization. Corresponding priorities and benefits were also established [1, 2].

The research of prominent scientists in the field of economic informatics and automated control systems, in particular G'ulomov S.S., is devoted to the issues of increasing the efficiency of the use and implementation of information and communication technologies in various sectors of the national economy [3].

The scientific works of Begalov B.A. cover the formation of information and communication technologies, their technological foundations, the development of the digital economy in the world and in Uzbekistan, as well as issues related to the introduction of ICT in enterprises. In turn, Odilov Sh.G' proposed approaches and recommendations for improving company logistics processes based on the application of information and communication technologies [3, 4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article uses monographic, expert and systematic analysis methods. The following methods were used: system analysis, factor analysis, and the views of leading scientists on improving the efficiency of remote service provision through the use of digital technologies.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

636 companies in January-May 2025 [IT Park Uzbekistan](#) received the status of resident. This indicates a steady growth in interest in the country as a new global IT hub. 369 of them were registered in Tashkent and 267 in the regions, which indicates the ongoing digitization and technological development throughout the country.

The high share of export-oriented companies is particularly noteworthy - 284 residents plan to provide services abroad, 117 of which are foreign companies. Export-oriented companies in the capital have targeted exports of more than \$46 million, while companies in the regions have targeted exports of more than \$31 million. This data highlights the contribution of the IT sector to the country's foreign exchange earnings and the development of the digital economy.

Resident companies are actively working in four main areas:

IT services (142 companies, of which 72 are foreign);

BPO (87 companies, including 19 foreign);

Service services (33 companies, 16 of them foreign);

Game development and creative industries (22 companies, 10 of which are foreign).

In May 2025, 116 new companies were registered in the IT Park, bringing the total number of residents to 2,846. 51 export-oriented companies, 22 of which are companies with foreign capital, received the status of IT Park residents. The companies were established in countries such as the USA, Japan, Korea, Great Britain, France, Jordan, Romania, Spain, Iran and Pakistan. Their structure of activity includes:

23 companies provide BPO and other services;

17 are working on creating IT products;

7 one specializes in IT services;

4 are developing in the creative industries.

In May, 17 companies received export-oriented resident status at the IT Park regional offices, 7 of which are companies with foreign capital. They are expected to create more than 235 jobs and ensure exports of more than \$2.6 million.

Among the new residents of the IT Park with foreign capital are technology companies providing export services in the fields of artificial intelligence, engineering, BPO and EdTech. Their geography of activity covers the regions of Europe, the Middle East, Asia and Australia, including:

“OSYSTEMS” (Spain, Jordan) it is implementing its own program to develop, train, and deploy autonomous artificial intelligence models specializing in data analysis for the Jordanian, Qatari, and US markets.

“FORTIS INSTRUMENTS SOUTH” (France) provides engineering services in the field of radiation monitoring, providing a high level of technological expertise for the French market.

“HUCORP GLOBAL” (Korea) is engaged in the localization of educational content and its export to Korea, contributing to the development of the EdTech sector internationally.

“EUROANSWER” (Romania) provides comprehensive BPO services for clients in Western Europe, including technical support and customer service for the German, French, Spanish, and Italian markets.

UNITLAB AI (USA) offers a data annotation platform equipped with its own AI-based automatic annotation models and workflow management tools. The company is engaged in outsourcing services to Germany, Australia, and France.

Data for the first five months of 2025 show that Uzbekistan is strengthening its position on the global IT map as a country with a favorable ecosystem for starting and expanding a business. The growth of exporters and foreign capital in the IT Park residents reflects the confidence of international investors and companies. The steady expansion into regions and the sophistication of the range of services provided indicate that the country’s IT market has reached a new level of maturity.

Interest in Uzbekistan among foreign entrepreneurs remains stable: since the beginning of the year, 164 companies with foreign capital have joined the ranks of IT Park residents. In total, the geography of residents covers 61 countries, including new destinations such as Jordan, Hong Kong, Indonesia, Liechtenstein, New Zealand and Norway.

The growth rates of companies from a number of countries are particularly noteworthy: in 2025, the number of Japanese residents doubled, those from China increased by 71 percent, those from Turkey by 133 percent, and those from Azerbaijan by 67 percent. These indicators clearly confirm the attractiveness of the local IT market for international business.

There is also a growing share of BPO and service companies that are starting to provide more complex and high-profit services, such as consulting on training, business analysis, technical documentation, and statistical data preparation. This indicates an increasing level of professionalism among Uzbek teams.

Uzbekistan [IT services](#) the number of exporters increased by 70% in the first nine months of this year. By the end of September, 936 enterprises within the IT Park exported digital services to 78 countries, a significant increase compared to 58 countries last year.

The growth in export activity is significant, with more than a third of IT Park residents earning income from international trade. Among the new exporters, just over half are engaged in the provision of IT services, such as software development, modification and technical support. In addition, 190 companies operate in outsourcing services, and 21 enterprises operate in the creative industry and GameDev sector.

Regional developments are also noteworthy: 191 exporting companies have started operating across the country. The volume of IT services provided to foreign countries has increased by 374%. Tashkent region leads with 32 enterprises, followed by Samarkand with 29 and Jizzakh with 17.

In the third quarter alone, 84 joint ventures and a total of more than 200 IT companies with foreign participation were established. These enterprises were founded by investors from 52 countries, including the USA, Great Britain, Germany, France, China, Japan, the UAE, India and Singapore.

The geography of Uzbekistan exports of digital products and services is notable for covering 78 countries. North America remains the largest market - 45% of foreign revenues fall on this region. The CIS countries and the Asia-Pacific region account for 27%, the share of European markets is 21%, and the Middle East and North Africa countries are 6%.

In mid-October, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev announced new incentives for export-oriented IT companies founded by foreign founders. The reforms include a reduction in income tax and corporate tax rates to 5%, aimed at creating a more favorable environment for international business.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, we can note that supporting startups gives an additional impetus to the development of the creative economy: this year, \$50 million has been allocated for their financing. These funds will be directed to the development of youth initiatives and the attraction of compatriots working in international companies.

The volume of IT services is expected to increase by 30% to 80 trillion soums, and exports will exceed \$1 billion. Digitalization of regions and industries will remain an important direction.

The specific features and specific aspects of the development of the field of remote services were studied, the volume of services provided by types of economic activity in our country and trends in their growth rates were analyzed. Reforms aimed at the accelerated development of these sectors were also studied, and proposals were developed for further development of the service sector based on innovative tools and methods and increasing economic efficiency in the sector.

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